
PARENTAL WICCAPHOBIA AND DELINQUENT BEHAVIOUR AMONG STREET CHILDREN IN MAJOR TOWNS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Fear of witchcraft is widespread in Akwa Ibom State, and because of this obnoxious supernatural belief, children accused of witchcraft are subjected to cruel treatment, many of whom turn to the streets and engage in various unwholesome behaviours in order to survive. The study examined how parental wiccaphobia predisposes street children to delinquent behavior in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The research, guided by *Albert Cohen's Subculture Theory*, used a descriptive survey design and stratified, purposive, and convenience sampling techniques were employed to select 200 street children aged 7-17 years from Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns. The data were collected through Focused Group Discussions and In-depth Interviews, and analysed using thematic analysis. The results showed that children accused of witchcraft were stigmatised, neglected, or abandoned due to parental wiccaphobia. These children were often abandoned on the streets after being evicted from their homes without supervision, stability, or assistance. This cycle of vulnerability and criminal activity is sustained, as their propensity to engage in delinquent behaviour increases due to trauma and marginalisation. The study suggested that community involvement and public education should be combined to protect children and debunk myths about witchcraft. Rehabilitation and strengthened social support networks can help reintegrate impacted children into society and reduce their susceptibility to delinquency. The contribution to knowledge lies in highlighting the link between parental wiccaphobia and the vulnerability of street children to delinquent behaviour, emphasising the role of cultural beliefs in child neglect and its social consequences. Further research could explore the effectiveness of community-based interventions in changing harmful beliefs and mitigating their impact on children, as well as investigating long-term outcomes for rehabilitated street children.

Key Words: *Parental Wiccaphobia, Street Children, Delinquent Behaviour, Major Towns*

Introduction

Although the belief in witchcraft is widespread, allegations of witchcraft, particularly those of “child witches”, have been more common in recent years (Gershman, 2022). Witchcraft accusations against children have become a disturbing phenomenon in many communities, particularly in societies where cultural beliefs and superstitions hold significant sway (Essien & Ben, 2011; Chineyemba, 2019). Parental wiccaphobia, which refers to the fear of witchcraft by parents, has devastating consequences on the accused children. Such beliefs often lead to stigmatisation, abandonment, or outright abuse of these children, leaving them vulnerable and exposed to a life of hardship on the streets (*The Nigerian Tribune Editorial*, 2022; Ekpenyong & Udisi, 2016). The implications of this growing concern extend beyond the immediate suffering of the affected children, as their experiences of rejection and lack of proper care often led to negative behavioural patterns that pose challenges to societal stability (Asangausung, 2024; Mboho & Ndaeyo, 2019).

Superstition is the primary cause of strong belief in witchcraft (Chineyemba, 2019). The phenomenon of witchcraft was prevalent in the 1990s, with religious leaders claiming to deliver children from witchcraft spirits (Bratrud, 2017). However, some parents and care givers are now more convinced of the existence of “child witches” through pastors, prophets, prophetess, and other religious leaders. When a child is accused of witchcraft, they are often treated as monsters or outcasts.

People see such categories of children as those have the spiritual power to cause pains, misfortune, and untimely death. Many children labeled as witches and wizards face abuse, maltreatment, neglect, abandonment, and stigmatisation, leaving them vulnerable to rapists, ritualists, and child traffickers. In fact, majority of these children are roaming the streets of towns and cities in Nigeria.

In Akwa Ibom State, superstitious beliefs dominate cultural and social frameworks, leading to parental wiccaphobia that has contributed to the rising number of street children. Okonkwo et al. (2021), Chineyemba (2019) and Nelson & Brown (2011) agreed that the fear of witchcraft and labelling children as those practicing witchcraft have become a recurring decimal in Akwa Ibom State. In this part of Nigeria, there is a strong belief that any child who possesses the spirit of witchcraft has the capacity to kill, cause deadly illnesses and motor accident or misfortune to another person, especially immediate family members. In order to make children confess their guilt in witchcraft activities, they endure a great deal of maltreatment and abuses, making them to find shelter in the streets of towns and cities. Without access to proper care, support, or rehabilitation, they become susceptible to a host of survival-oriented behaviours, some of which are considered delinquent (begging, stealing, vandalism, gambling and many others). Over time, this not only affects their well-being but also has broader social implications, including increased crime rates and perpetuation of poverty cycles.

These violent attacks on children that have refused to stop are contrary to the provisions of the Child Rights Act (2003), a legal framework that protects the rights and privileges of children. Despite efforts by governmental and non-governmental organisations to address child abuse, the influence of parental wiccaphobia remains underexplored and underreported as a contributing factor. Understanding how this specific cultural belief shapes the behaviours and trajectories of street children is crucial for developing tailored interventions.

Previous studies including Agazue (2021) examined how African children are labelled as witches and wizards by their parents and guardians. Yoder et al. (2021) examined child witchcraft confessions as a distress in Sierra Leone. Priest et al. (2020) examined Christian pastors and alleged child witches in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo. Ekpenyong & Udisi (2016) examined the prevalence of street children in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Sanou (2015) examined how witchcraft accusations destroy family, community, and the Church. However, none of these studies focused on how parental wiccaphobia predisposes street children to delinquent behaviour in major towns in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This study addressed the gap, by exploring how parental wiccaphobia make street children susceptible to delinquent behaviour in Akwa Ibom State, so as to foster better-informed strategies for prevention and rehabilitation. This study provided answers to the question, how does parental wiccaphobia predispose street children to delinquent behaviour in Akwa Ibom State?

Literature Review

In Sierra Leone, child witchcraft was investigated by Yoder *et al.* (2021) as an idiom of distress. The study combined emic and etic viewpoints and used a qualitative method of data collection and analysis. One hundred and twenty-seven (127) persons participated in the study in Freetown, Sierra Leone. To determine the dangers and mitigating factors associated with accusations and admissions of witchcraft, inductive analysis was employed. The research determined protective and risk variables pertaining to the children, the family, peer relationships, educators and other careers, pastors, traditional healers, and the larger community. It was also discovered that confession of witchcraft is conducted by a traditional healer or pastor. The gap in the study is that it does not specifically address the role of parents' fear of witchcraft (wiccaphobia) in predisposing children to delinquent behaviour. This specific focus on parental wiccaphobia and its potential influence on children's behaviour represent a gap in the existing literature.

Priest *et al.* (2020) observed that those who accused others of practicing witchcraft increasingly seek confirmation from pastors, prophets, and intercessors. Based on the accusations made by the accusers, church authorities may affirm the presence of witchcraft. Additionally, according to Surrey Safeguarding Children Partnership (SSCP, 2023), parents, families, and the child themselves think that evil powers have taken possession of them and that they can use

those forces to hurt other people. Parents who think their child is possessed by an evil spirit can also speak in private with a traditional healer or spiritualist; usually, a religious leader, parents, or other family members perform the exorcism or deliverance. A youngster may suffer emotional abuse if regarded as having an evil spirit. Moreover, if an attempt is made to “deliver” or “exorcise” a bad spirit from the child, the child may suffer grave consequences, including being forced to leave the house and seek help on the streets. Sanou (2015) furthered that most parents who are traditional worshippers, Muslims and Christians fear witchcraft and they considered it as an excuse for social ills and always in an attempt to seek preventive and curative measures against witchcraft attacks. According to Sanou (2015), there are several children accused of witchcraft, especially those with disability, stubborn children and children with albinism. A child facing the fallout from a witchcraft allegation suffers long-term detrimental effects in numerous areas. Such a child experiences discrimination and stigma for the rest of his or her life if the child is accused of witchcraft. The troubles begin when parents and religious authorities abuse them in an attempt to coerce them into confessing to witchcraft or drive away the witch’s spirit from them. They might not be able to receive medical care since certain doctors frequently decline to handle kids who are thought to be witches. Since many parents will not send their children to a school where they can be accused of witchcraft, their right to education is violated. Instructors occasionally decline to let

students who are accused of witchcraft to attend their classes.

In addition, since their family and community have rejected or abandoned them, they are not always allowed to participate in family or community life. These youngsters wind out on the streets after being abandoned by their families, churches, communities, and even some government systems. Many of them develop drug and alcohol addictions, get HIV/AIDS, and are coerced into labour, or commit sexual offences. According to Onongha (2014), a highly concerning practice is that witch doctors are occasionally asked to assist in identifying suspected witches in churches when there are concerns of witchcraft among Christians.

Agazue (2021) examined child witchcraft in Africa, concentrating on female carers who abuse and murder children who are thought to be practicing witchcraft. To comprehend the causes of the abuse as well as the elements that contributed to these views, the research employed qualitative approaches. Information was obtained from media articles, NGOs, and interviews. Secondary reports on the mistreatment of women in other African countries were analysed for the study. The findings showed that women abused their children suspected to be witches and wizards due to what they watched in the movies, their religious affiliations, ignorance, misfortune, and discomfort. *The results imply that various factors, such as exposure to certain media, religious beliefs, lack of knowledge, unfortunate circumstances, and personal distress, can contribute to women abusing their children suspected to be witches or*

wizards. The gap in the study above is that it focuses on the abuse and murder of children suspected to be witches by female guardians in Africa, examining the various causes and contributing factors to such abuse. However, it does not specifically address the role of parents' fear of witchcraft (wiccaphobia) in predisposing children to delinquent behaviour. The current study aims to investigate how parents' fear of witchcraft influences children's delinquent behaviour. In their study, Ekpenyong & Udisi (2016) conducted research in Akwa Ibom State to determine the causes of the spread of street children other than economic reasons. Using observation and documented materials, the study included ninety-three (93) street children between the ages of four and eighteen. It was discovered that social issues, such as child witchcraft accusations, and other forms of abuses and violence exposed children to street life. Ekpenyong & Udisi's (2016) study have a flaw in that, although it notes that social issues such as accusations of child witchcraft play a role in children ending up on the streets, it does not particularly address the effect of parents' fear of witchcraft, or wiccaphobia, and how this may lead to their children engaging in delinquent behaviour.

Kanjanda & Chiparange (2015) studied street children accused of witchcraft within Christians in the city of Mutare, Zimbabwe. The convenience, purposive, and stratified sampling techniques were used to choose a sample size of 50 individuals. Direct observations, semi-structured interviews, and an open-ended questionnaire were used to gather the data. The gathered information was examined using descriptive analysis.

The findings demonstrated that Christian parents in Mutare City exposed their children to the streets because of witchcraft accusations, which leads to the development of anti-social subculture. It was suggested that faith-based organisations should resist any actions that could lead a child to become homeless. The gap in the study above is that while it acknowledges the influence of parents' fear of witchcraft (wiccaphobia) on children being exposed to street life and developing an anti-social subculture, it does not specifically focus on delinquent behaviour as a result of wiccaphobia. The current study on wiccaphobia and its potential influence on children's delinquent behaviour could provide a more in-depth exploration of the specific impact this fear has on children's actions and attitudes, contributing to a better understanding of the mechanisms at play.

Mhizha (2013), investigated the behaviour and religious-spiritual self-image of street children in Harare, Zimbabwe. The design of the study was psycho-ethnographic. There were 22 volunteers in the study. Six key informants from Harare, Zimbabwe, and sixteen street children, ages 12 to 18, were the participants. Samples were chosen using the purposive and snowball sampling strategies. Focus group discussions, in-depth interviews, and observation techniques were the data collection techniques used. The data were analysed using the theme content analytical approach. The findings demonstrated that there was a general negative perception of street children's spirituality and religion. Many homeless children thought that their loved ones were putting bad spells on them and that they

were under the grip of evil spirits. The detrimental perception that street children have of themselves on a religious and spiritual level has a major effect on their social reactions, moral behaviour, and psychological well-being. The gap in the study above is that while it discusses the negative perception of spirituality and religion among street children, it does not specifically address the role of parents' fear of witchcraft (wiccaphobia) in predisposing children to delinquent behaviour. The current study focuses on wiccaphobia and its potential influence on children's delinquent behaviour, which provides a more targeted exploration of this specific aspect.

In summary, the examined literature shows that street children's delinquent dispositions might be greatly influenced by their parents' belief in witchcraft. These cultural and social beliefs frequently lead to situations that encourage abuse, neglect, and social isolation, which push children into the streets and increase their involvement in criminal activity. Children who are stigmatized and rejected by their families and communities may be severely accused of being witches or possessed. They may run to the streets as a result of this social exclusion, where they are exposed to deviant behaviour as a coping mechanism for their loneliness and a way to survive. Witchcraft-related beliefs held by parents can result in abusive behaviour against their children, such as beatings, ritualistic washings, and other damaging procedures meant to "cure" them. Children who experience such abuse may develop psychological trauma and a lack of trust in adults, which may lead them to run away from home and participate in

criminal activities. Parents who think their child is a witch might stop providing the child with emotional and material assistance, ignoring the child's fundamental needs.

Children who experience neglect may be forced to turn to stealing, begging, or other criminal actions in order to find resources and support on the streets. Negative societal practices may encourage the mistreatment of children suspected of witchcraft in their communities, especially where the belief in the practice is widespread. Children may find it difficult to acquire acceptance and support as a result of this social reinforcement, which raises the possibility that they may turn to crime on the streets. When a child is accused of witchcraft, they may suffer from serious psychological consequences like low self-esteem, depression and anxiety. These psychological health issues may exacerbate behavioural disorders and raise the likelihood of committing crimes.

Theoretical Framework

This study was guided by the assumptions of Albert Cohen's Subculture Theory. Albert K. Cohen, an American sociologist and criminologist from Boston, Massachusetts was born 1918 and died in 2014 (Asangausung, 2024). Cohen was particularly valued for his Subculture Theory of delinquency, which occupies an important place in the sociology of crime and delinquency. Albert K. Cohen's Subculture Theory provides a framework that can help explain the delinquent behaviour of street children in Akwa Ibom State, particularly those affected by parental wiccaphobia and societal accusations of

witchcraft. Cohen asserts that children are more prone to exhibit behaviours deemed deviant or delinquent when they are raised in a subculture with values and standards that differ from those of the general population. This occurs because the children, often from disadvantaged backgrounds, are unable to meet the expectations and standards imposed by the dominant social structures, leading them to seek out alternative subcultures where they can gain acceptance and status.

In the context of this study, parental wiccaphobia acts as a cultural factor that reinforces a subculture of rejection, where accusations of witchcraft force children into a position of marginalisation and social exclusion. These children, abandoned or abused by their families due to superstition or cultural beliefs, are rejected by the dominant social order that values family cohesion and communal support. Consequently, they seek belonging within an alternative, underground subculture: the world of street life. This subculture is characterised by delinquent behaviour such as begging, petty theft, substance abuse, and gang affiliation, all of which are coping mechanisms for survival in the face of adversity and a lack of societal protection.

According to Cohen's theory, the children do not conform to the conventional norms of behaviour because they lack the legitimate means (i.e., support from family, education, or social institutions) to achieve socially valued goals such as security, care, and opportunity. Instead, they embrace behaviours that provide them with a sense of self-worth and status within the street subculture, albeit through illegal or socially harmful means. Thus, parental wiccaphobia

exacerbates their vulnerability, creating a fertile ground for the development of this subculture of delinquency. This theory explains how the hostile environments created by parental abuse and societal rejection drive these children into alternative subcultures, where they respond to their stigmatization and victimization by adopting behaviour that would otherwise be considered deviant by mainstream society.

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive survey design. The reason for using the descriptive survey design was to describe the experiences of children (male and female), who live permanently and independently on the streets of Akwa Ibom State. The data for this study were gathered from the emic perspective using mixed methods technique. The research was entirely qualitative and was based on the primary data obtained from the street children, who participated in a study that concerns them. Three (3) significant towns in Akwa Ibom State were specifically chosen for this study's investigation. These towns were Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene and they were picked because of the large number of street children living these locations. As noted by Ekpenyong & Udisi (2016), Akwa Ibom State is among the states in Nigeria with a high concentration of street children in the major streets of some local Government Areas.

The target group was children living permanently on the streets of Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene. They live in these towns without the help of their parents or family members. They are street children between the ages of 7 and 17, and these children were

included in the study because they are the ones who understand the hardships of living and surviving on the streets without their parents. As such, they are best suited to share their experiences and difficulties without considering the opinions of others around them. The number of street children in Akwa Ibom State remains unknown due to an absence of statistics (Ukpong, 2021). The inclusion of street children for this study was because they are the experts on their own experiences and challenges. Allowing them to participate gives them a direct voice in a study that impacts their lives. The inclusion criterion was that selected street children have to be found within Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns of Akwa Ibom State. Street children who were less than 7 years and above 18 years were not part of the study.

Two hundred (200) street children (159 males and 41 females), who were 7-17 years old and lived permanently and independently on the streets of Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns, made up the study sample size. Since this was a qualitative survey, determining the sample size using a recognised statistical technique was not necessary. Rather, the sample size for this

Table 1: Sample allocation according to LGAs and methods of data collection

Study Location	FGD	IDI	Total
Uyo	72 (8 sessions of 9 street children each)	13	85
Eket	45 (5 sessions of 9 street children each)	6	51
Ikot Ekpene	54 (6 sessions of 9 street children each)	10	64
Total	171(19 sessions of 9 street children each)	29	200

Source: Field data (2025).

The sample distribution according to LGAs and data collection techniques is displayed in Table 1. Out of the 200 street children who live constantly on the streets without

study was determined through data redundancy or saturation, or the point at which gathering more data would no longer yield new information relevant to the research objectives. A total of 19 focus group discussions (FGDs) with nine (9) street children from each group were held, and 29 in-depth interviews with 29 street children were also held. At the 19th FGD session and the 29th in-depth interview, data redundancy or saturation was attained. The studies of Rahimi & Khatooni (2024), Daher (2023), Hennink & Kaiser (2022), and Glasser & Strauss (2017) provided support for this technique of choosing a sample size in a qualitative survey.

Sampling technique is the process of choosing a subset of people, objects, or observations from a larger population in order to perform research or analysis. The validity and reliability of study findings can be strongly impacted by the sampling technique selected (Rahimi & Khatooni, 2024). The stratified, purposive, and convenience sampling techniques were employed in the selection of street children in Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene towns.

their parents or guardians, 85 of them were from Uyo town, 51 were from Eket town and 64 of them were from Ikot Ekpene town. Twenty-nine (29) street children participated

in the IDI, while 171 street children participated in the FGD.

Focused Group Discussion (FGD) and In-depth interview (IDI) were used for data collection in this study. The researchers developed an interview schedule for both FGD and IDI, which was divided into sections, to aid the collection of qualitative data. The street children are transient population, as such; they were traced to locations on the streets of Uyo, Eket, and Ikot Ekpene towns and solicited their participation in the study. All the study participants gave their oral consent after discussing the goals of the investigation with them.

Nineteen (19) sessions of the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) (9 participants per group) with one hundred and seventy-one (171) street children participated in the FGDs, while twenty-nine (29) street children took part in the IDIs that were held throughout the study locations using the interview schedule. Prior to the interview sessions, quiet locations were selected for ease. The socio-demographic information of the street children was collected before the actual discussion or interview began. Every FGD and IDI session was tape recorded to aid transcriptions, and field notes were also collected concurrently. The interviews were conducted in Ibibio, Annang, and Oro

languages. For individuals unfamiliar with the local languages, pidgin and plain English were suitable. To assist with gathering primary data, three (3) research assistants (RAs) were engaged.

The interview schedule was used to gather qualitative data for the study. The data collected from 200 street children were presented descriptively and analysed in themes. The frequency distribution tables and simple percentages were used to present the personal information of street children and the qualitative data were analysed through thematic analysis method. The excerpts of the transcribed data obtained from the FGDs and IDIs served as the basis for the analysis.

The oral consent was provided by all of the street children who voluntarily participated in the study. The research participants were made aware that their participation in the study was completely optional, that they could withdraw at any time without consequence, and that there would be no negative consequences associated with their decision to take part or not. The respondents were assured of their right to confidentiality and privacy. The researcher prioritised the children's comfort, safety, and autonomy throughout the process. This helped them feel comfortable sharing information and reduces the risk of exploitation.

Results

Table 2: Distribution of street children according to their personal information (N = 200)

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Town of Residence:		
Uyo	85	42.50
Eket	51	25.50
Ikot Ekpene	64	32.00
Sex:		
Male	159	79.50
Female	41	20.50
Age bracket		
7-9 years	60	30.00
10-12 years	57	28.50
13-15 years	48	24.00
16-17 years	35	17.50
Level of educational attainment:		
Never attended school	50	25.00
Not completed primary school	81	40.50
Completed primary school	40	20.00
Not completed secondary school	29	14.50
Completed secondary school	0	0.00
Custodial role before taking to street life		
Mother	14	7.00
Father	55	27.50
Both parents	20	10.00
Step parent	91	45.50
Guardian	20	10.00

Source: Field data (2025)

Table 2 shows the distribution of street children based on their personal information. Results showed that 85 street children, representing 42.50 per cent, were from Uyo town, 51 street children, representing 25.50 per cent, were from Eket town, and 64 street children, representing 32.00 per cent, and were from Ikot Ekpene town, respectively. This suggests that street children were predominant in Uyo and Ikot Ekpene towns

than in Eket town. This suggests that there may be greater rates of unemployment, poverty, or limited access to economic and educational possibilities in these areas, which would make it difficult for families to provide for their kids and encourage family instability. **There may be social issues such as family breakdown, domestic violence, or substance abuse that contributed to children ending up on the streets. The**

towns might have limited resources for providing social services and support for vulnerable families and children. Rapid growth in urban areas like Uyo and Ikot Ekpene can lead to migration from rural areas in search of better opportunities, but not all families are able to find stable housing or employment.

The results further showed that 159 (79.50%) street children were males and 41 (20.50%) of them were females. As a result, most street children in the research area were boys. One possible explanation for the greater proportion of male street children than female street children could be a confluence of cultural, social, and economic variables. These could include inequalities in social support networks, gender-based discrepancies in opportunity, and social norms that could encourage males to be more independent. In some towns, these variables may make it more likely for boys than girls to end up on the streets.

Of the street children, 60 (30%) were between the ages of 7 and 9 years; 57 (28.50%) were between the ages of 10 and 12 years; 48 (24%) were between the ages of 13 and 15 years; and 35 (17.50%) were between the ages of 16 and 17 years. In Akwa Ibom State, the average age of street children was 11.78 years, while the standard deviation was 3.09 years. The average age which is 11.78 years suggests that the overall age distribution of street children centres 11-12 years of age, which makes sense as two of the groups (7-9 and 10-12 years old) accounted for more than half the total participants. The standard deviation measures how spread out the ages were from the mean. A standard deviation of 3.09 years

indicated a moderate variation in ages around the mean of 11.78 years. Most of the ages of street children will typically fall within 3 years above or below the mean (roughly between 8.7 and 14.8 years). In summary, the result suggests that there is a downward trend as the ages of street children increases.

This implies that street children face high risks of illness, malnutrition, violence, accidents, and inadequate healthcare, which can lead to early mortality. Older children who have spent extended periods on the streets are more vulnerable to chronic health issues, substance abuse and violence, which increases the risk of death as they aged. Also, older street children are often at higher risk of coming into conflict with the law, either due to minor offences or because they may turn to theft, substance use or gang involvement as a means of survival. Law enforcement agencies might target them more than younger children, leading to higher rates of arrest and incarceration among older street children. Older street children sometimes move to different locations for better opportunities, leaving areas where they were previously counted or observed. The harsh condition of living in the streets significantly contributed to decrease in number of older street children, as they often face more severe consequences than younger children.

Concerning the educational attainment of street children in the study area, the results showed that 50 (25%) of the street children had never gone to school; 81 (40.50%) had not finished primary school; 40 (20%) had completed primary school; 29 (14.50%) of the street children had entered secondary

school but had given up at a certain point; and none of the street children had finished secondary school. The interpretation of the educational attainment results for street children in the study area showed that a significant proportion of 25 per cent of the street children studied had never attended school, indicating a lack of access to education or disengagement with formal schooling. The result indicated that 40.50 per cent had not finished primary school, and 14.50 cent had entered secondary school but discontinued their education at some point. This highlights a concerning pattern of low completion rates for primary and secondary education among street children in the study area. Only 20 per cent of street children had completed primary school, and none had finished secondary school, indicating limited educational achievement among this group. Overall, these results highlighted a concerning lack of educational opportunities and achievement among street children in the study area, signaling a need for targeted interventions to improve their access to education and support their academic success.

The results also showed the relationship between the custodians of street children, before taking to street life. Of the total number of street children, 91 (45.50%) reported living with their stepparents, 55 (27.50%) with their dads, 20 (10%) with their guardians, 20 (10%) with both parents, and 14 (7%) with their moms. It suggests that before they were ostracised or ran away from their homes, the majority of street children stayed with their fathers and stepparents. *The result suggests that most of these street children did not have stable, supportive family structures. Living primarily*

with stepparents or fathers indicates that many children may have lacked the emotional and psychological support needed for healthy development. This instability, compounded by possible neglect or conflict within these living arrangements, likely contributed to decision to leave home or being pushed out, leading to street life.

Analysis of Qualitative Data

In an attempt to answer research question about how parental wiccaphobia predisposes street children to delinquent behaviour, the data gathered from the street children during FGDs and IDIs revealed that parental wiccaphobia or the fear of witchcraft has a detrimental effect on the lives of the accused children and subsequently exposes them to delinquent behaviour. The narratives provided by the street children revealed the severe emotional, physical, and psychological harm caused by wrongful accusations of witchcraft. In each case, the accusations led to abandonment, torture, and isolation, often by family members, religious leaders, and community figures. These children faced extreme neglect and rejection, which drove them to seek refuge on the streets. Forced into survival mode, many resorted to petty theft, joining gangs, drug use, or engaging in informal work, such as washing car windscreens. They spoke of the traumatic effects of being labeled as witches, including the abuse they endured during exorcism rituals and the stigmatization they faced within their communities. Despite being innocent, these children were pushed into marginalisation, with little to no support from the very institutions and individuals

that should have protected them. These narratives underscore the destructive power of superstition, some cultural practices, and societal neglect. When the participants were asked about their experiences at home when they were accused of witchcraft, the excerpts of the interviews revealed thus:

A 12-year-old street child said, "*My parents and other close relatives accused me of practicing witchcraft and they were beating and torturing me as they like. I was physically and psychologically devastated by the terrible event. For fear of death, I run away from home*".(FGD/male/Uyo/January 10, 2025).

The information given by the 12-year-old reflects the intense physical and psychological suffering inflicted on him due to wrongful accusations of witchcraft, particularly when such accusations come from family members. The child's recount of being beaten and tortured by close relatives highlights the deep betrayal and the eroded sense of security that a child should find in their home. The overwhelming emotional and physical devastation the child endured demonstrates the severe impact that both familial violence and the stigma of witchcraft allegations can have on a vulnerable child. Daniel, Udousoro & Umoh, (2024), observed that factors such as economy, insecurity, fear of the unknown and some psychological uncertainty incite the escape of young people from social and cultural imprisonment in homogenous to heterogeneous areas.

Another 14-year-old street child added, "*When I was accused a witch, my parents took me to one native doctor to rid myself of any witchcraft. I will always remember it as*

a horrific and agonising experience..."(FGD/male/Uyo/January 12, 2025).

The data from the 14-year-old highlights the extreme measures parents sometimes take, driven by beliefs in witchcraft, which can further exacerbate the trauma experienced by children accused of such. Being taken to a native doctor for exorcism or "cures" reveals a deeply harmful response based on superstition, demonstrating how traditional practices, rooted in fear and misbelief, can be inflicted upon children under the guise of healing. The child's recollection of the experience as horrific and agonising emphasises the intense emotional and physical suffering these children endure. This situation not only reflects the misuse of power by family members who should be offering protection but also illustrates the lasting psychological scars left by abusive rituals meant to eradicate something that is, in reality, a social construct.

Yet, another 10-year-old street child said, "*Pastors and prophets called me a witch, making my parents and other family members to abandon me without any care. I was left alone, without anybody to turn to or ask for some help and when I saw these my friends, I joined them. we use to sleep in fields every night and in the day time we beg commuter for money to buy water and food...*" (IDI/male/Uyo/January 14, 2025).

The testimony of the 10-year-old reveals the devastating effects of religious figures, such as pastors and prophets, contributing to the stigma of witchcraft accusations. The child's statement shows how the power and influence of religious authorities can play a harmful role, encouraging parents and

family members to abandon their child in the face of such unfounded allegations. The emotional and physical neglect that followed highlights the deep sense of rejection, leaving the child without any support system. With no one to turn to, the child was forced to navigate life alone on the streets, demonstrating how the absence of compassionate intervention can push vulnerable individuals to the fringes of society.

An 8-year-old street child said: *“I was driven from my home and left homeless and hungry on the streets after being accused of witchcraft. I had trouble finding food or shelter because of the stigma associated with the accusation...”*(IDI/female/Uyo/January 14, 2025).

The statement from the 8-year-old child reflects the profound and devastating consequences of being falsely accused of witchcraft at such a young age. The accusation not only led to being driven from home but also left the child vulnerable to hunger, homelessness, and extreme hardship, highlighting the social isolation and stigma that accompany such allegations. The difficulty the child faced in securing food or shelter further underscores the precariousness of street life, where the lack of support and the weight of societal rejection make basic survival a daily struggle. This testimony speaks to the deep emotional and physical toll that false accusations take, as well as the need for immediate intervention to protect and care for children who are unjustly abandoned.

Yet, another 7-year-old street child added, *“I was forced out of the house after*

being accused of witchcraft, leaving me vulnerable and without a way to live. I considered seeking refuge on the street as the best option...”(FGD/male/Eket/January 18, 2025). The response from the 7-year-old highlights the intersection of cultural beliefs and societal vulnerabilities, demonstrating how accusations of witchcraft, often rooted in cultural superstitions, can devastate children’s lives. Forced out of the house at such a tender age, the child faced abandonment and rejection, leading to exposure to the harsh realities of life on the street. This reflects systemic societal failures, including the lack of protective mechanisms for children falsely accused or ostracized due to deep-seated traditional practices. The choice to seek refuge on the street indicates a perceived absence of alternative support systems, revealing gaps in social welfare and child protection structures in the area.

An 11-year-old street child said, *“I was stigmatized after being accused of being a witch, which resulted in continuous physical abuse, neglect, hunger, and isolation and I had to leave the home for my step mother...”*(IDI/male/Eket/January 21, 2025). The response from the 11-year-old underscores the profound and multi-layered impact of stigma associated with witchcraft accusations, particularly on vulnerable children. This stigmatization led to severe consequences, including physical abuse, neglect, hunger, and isolation, highlighting the emotional and physical toll such accusations can inflict. The child’s decision to leave home due to the actions of a stepmother reveals familial dynamics that often exacerbate vulnerabilities, with stepparents sometimes being implicated in

acts of neglect or hostility. This account reflects broader systemic and cultural challenges, where harmful traditional beliefs go unchecked, leaving children unprotected and forced into precarious circumstances. It emphasizes the critical need for societal reform, community education, and stronger mechanisms for child protection to combat these harmful practices and provide support for children caught in such situations.

Another 13-year-old street child said, *“Due to allegations of witchcraft, I was tortured by church pastors and traditional healers in an attempt to exorcise me, which made my trauma worse...”* (FGD/male/Ikot Ekpene/January 22, 2025). The account of the 13-year-old reveals the deeply traumatic and abusive practices inflicted on children accused of witchcraft, emphasizing the harmful role played by certain religious and traditional institutions. The involvement of pastors or traditional healers in torturous exorcism practices points to the exploitation of cultural fears and superstitions, often resulting in severe physical and psychological harm to the child. This statement emphasises how deeply entrenched beliefs can perpetuate abuse under the guise of spiritual intervention. The increased trauma experienced by the child highlights the failure of societal structures to protect them, while also exposing a disturbing overlap between misguided religious practices and harmful cultural traditions.

A 15-year-old street child said, *“I was falsely accused of practicing witchcraft and I was abandoned by relatives who did not want to be associated with someone who was accused of witchcraft; I was left to live in*

difficult circumstances on the streets by myself...”(IDI/female/Ikot Ekpene/January 27, 2025). The testimony of the 15-year-old reveals the isolating and life-altering consequences of false accusations of witchcraft, particularly when such accusations lead to familial abandonment. This rejection not only reflects the deep stigma attached to witchcraft allegations but also exposes the vulnerability of children who become scapegoats for societal fears and superstitions. Left to fend for herself, the child’s circumstances highlight the precariousness of life on the streets, where survival becomes an immense challenge in the absence of familial or community support. This narrative underscores the pervasive impact of harmful cultural beliefs and the failure of protective systems to intervene.

When asked if they have indulged in delinquent behaviour as a result of being exposed to street life due to labelling them as witchcraft, a 13-year-old street child said, *“I was forced out of our house and left without any other option of getting food or shelter, so I turned to petty stealing as a means of survival. I prefer living on the street than to stay with my parents who pushed me away. For your information, I am not a witch as people perceive it...”*(FGD/male/Uyo/January10, 2025). The narrative of the 13-year-old illustrates the desperation and resilience of a child forced into homelessness due to wrongful accusations of witchcraft. The push factor of being ostracized by parents not only underscores the emotional and psychological trauma inflicted but also highlights the dire socioeconomic consequences that lead

children to resort to survival strategies like petty theft. The child's preference for life on the street over staying with abusive parents indicates profound betrayal and dysfunction within the family unit, fueled by harmful societal beliefs. Their assertion of innocence against the accusations further emphasises the injustice faced and the stigma endured. This account reflects the broader failures in safeguarding children from cultural misconceptions and societal neglect.

Yet, another 10-year-old street child added, *"I had to join gangs for safety because I felt isolated and ostracised by the unfounded accusation of witchcraft..."* (FGD/male/Uyo/January 15, 2025). The statement of the 10-year-old sheds light on the far-reaching consequences of isolation and stigmatization stemming from witchcraft accusations. Forced into a life on the streets, the child sought safety and belonging by joining gangs, a choice that underscores the lack of protective support systems and the vulnerability of children in such circumstances. This decision reflects the limited options available to marginalized and ostracized individuals, particularly in hostile environments where they are left to navigate threats alone. The unfounded nature of the accusations further highlights the injustice of the situation and the societal complicity in pushing children into perilous environments.

A 15-year-old street child said, *"I was wrongfully accused of being a witch, which made me angry at the injustice because I am not a witch. I had no option but to flee to the street and survive through thievery, scrap-picking, drug use, and sometimes begging..."* (IDI/male/Uyo/January 14,

2025). The testimony of the 15-year-old reflects the profound sense of injustice and frustration experienced by children accused of witchcraft, driving them to escape abusive environments and adapt to the harsh realities of street life. The child's anger at the wrongful accusation highlights the emotional toll of being stigmatized without evidence, a reflection of deep societal and cultural failures. Survival through theft, scrap-picking, drug use, and begging underscores the severe challenges faced by street children, revealing the lack of alternative support systems or viable opportunities for self-sufficiency. This narrative highlights the cumulative effects of ostracisation, pushing children into precarious livelihoods and exposing them to greater risks.

Another 12-year-old street child said, *"This issue of witchcraft accusations forced me to become a traffic stop windscreen washer since I had no other way to make money after being shunned by my community over speculative allegations..."* (FGD/male/Eket/January16, 2025). The account of the 12-year-old illustrates the harsh realities faced by children accused of witchcraft and subsequently ostracized by their communities. The speculative nature of the allegations underscores the irrationality and injustice of such stigmatization. The child turning to washing windcreens at traffic stops for survival highlights both their resourcefulness and the lack of institutional or communal support to address their needs. This experience reflects the economic and social marginalization stemming from unfounded accusations, forcing vulnerable

individuals into low-income, informal labour to sustain themselves.

A 15-year-old street child said: *“After allegations, being wrongly labelled led to a shift towards drug use as a way to cope with the stress caused by social abuse...”* (IDI/male/Eket/January 21, 2025). The statement of the 15-year-old highlights the profound psychological impact of being wrongfully labelled as a witch, leading to substance abuse as a coping mechanism. This response to stress and social abuse underscores the emotional toll of stigmatization and the absence of adequate support systems to address the trauma experienced by such children. The reliance on drugs reflects a desperate attempt to escape the overwhelming reality of rejection, discrimination, and abuse. This narrative underscores the cyclical nature of societal neglect, where false accusations not only ostracize children but also push them toward harmful behaviours, further perpetuating their vulnerability.

Yet, another 11-year-old street child added, *“After being abandoned by my parents, I turned to stealing as a method of survival due to false accusations of being a witch...”* (FGD/female/Ikot Ekpen/January 28, 2025). The account of the 11-year-old highlights the devastating consequences of parental abandonment driven by unfounded accusations of witchcraft. This forced separation not only leaves the child emotionally scarred but also compels them to resort to survival strategies like theft, a reflection of the dire circumstances they face. The narrative exposes the failure of societal and familial structures to provide care and protection, especially when harmful beliefs

lead to neglect and rejection. It also underscores the stigma and systemic injustices associated with witchcraft accusations, which push vulnerable children into marginalized and precarious lifestyles.

In sum, the FGD and IDI excerpts showed that being accused of witchcraft led to delinquent behaviour in street children because they were frequently ostracised, abandoned, and rejected by their parents, guardians and other family members/communities. They were compelled by their isolation to live on the streets, where they battled for survival in the absence of guidance or support. The stigma of being labelled a witch led to internalised anger, resentment, and a lack of self-worth, pushing them toward delinquent activities as means of coping, seeking revenge, or simply surviving. Without a safe environment or positive role models, they engaged in theft, substance abuse, or join gangs, as these become the only available avenues for acceptance and survival.

Discussion of Findings

The results revealed that parental wiccaphobia significantly contributed to the delinquent behaviour of street children, reflecting a complex interplay between cultural beliefs and child welfare. When parents, guardians, or relatives accuse children of practicing witchcraft, it often leads to severe consequences including starvation, abandonment, and physical abuse. These unfounded accusations are frequently fueled by religious leaders or traditional healers who engage in exorcisms, further deepening the child's plight. The resultant stigma and harsh treatment drive these children to the streets, where they face

extreme survival pressures. The lack of support and the harsh realities of street life compel them to engage in delinquent behaviour such as begging, theft, or substance abuse as means of coping with their harsh new environmental reality. In essence, the fear and accusations surrounding witchcraft exacerbate the vulnerabilities of these children, pushing them towards behaviour that are often a direct response to their abusive and neglectful experiences.

The findings from the testimonies of street children accused of witchcraft highlighted profound emotional, physical, and psychological harm resulting from wrongful accusations, which are often perpetuated by family members, religious figures, and community members. The recurring theme across these accounts is the betrayal children experienced when those closest to them, typically parents, relatives, or caregivers were the ones who turned against them based on unfounded beliefs in witchcraft. These children experienced various forms of physical and psychological abuse, including beatings, torture, and stigmatization, with many feelings forced to flee their homes in search of safety and survival. This abandonment was not only a loss of security but also marked the beginning of a life filled with severe hardships, such as homelessness, hunger, and isolation.

What stands out across these narratives is the absence of support structures to help these children in their time of need. This lack of support pushed many to resort to street survival strategies, including petty theft, begging, scrap-picking, and joining gangs for safety or to have a sense of

belonging. These behaviours, often deemed "delinquent," were acts of necessity born from the acute lack of viable alternatives. The deep sense of rejection left them vulnerable to exploitation and further trauma. Moreover, their coping mechanisms, such as drug use or participating in menial work like washing car windscreens, signify both their resourcefulness in surviving on the streets and the absence of institutional or community support systems to address their underlying needs.

Another key finding is the deeply ingrained role of cultural and traditional beliefs in perpetuating violence and rejection against these children. Both religious figures and traditional healers were often involved in practices intended to "exorcise" or rid children of witchcraft, adding to the physical and emotional trauma. These are you 1beliefs, coupled with the authority vested in such figures, only compounded the children's suffering. What emerged from these accounts was a pattern of cultural practices and societal expectations that isolate children, subject them to violence, and ultimately force them to navigate a hostile world without protection or understanding. These findings are supported by the works of Yoder *et al.* (2021), Agazue (2021), Priest *et al.* (2020), Sanou (2015), and Kanjanda & Chiparange (2015), who observed that many children accused of witchcraft had been abused, malnourished, ostracised, and compelled to leave their homes and became street children.

Conclusion

This study examined how parental wiccaphobia predisposes street children to delinquent behaviour in major towns in

Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Results showed that parental wiccaphobia is a significant factor in the delinquent behaviour of street children, as it exacerbates their vulnerabilities and leads to severe consequences such as starvation, abandonment, and physical abuse. These accusations are often fueled by religious leaders or traditional healers who engage in exorcisms, these acts further deepen their plight. The lack of support and harsh realities of street life compel these children to engage in delinquent behaviours such as begging, theft, or substance abuse. The fear and accusations surrounding witchcraft exacerbate the vulnerabilities of these children, pushing them towards behaviours that are often a direct response to their abusive and neglectful experiences. The absence of support structures and deeply ingrained cultural and traditional beliefs further perpetuates violence and rejection against these children, forcing them to navigate to a hostile world without protection or understanding.

This study contributes to knowledge by establishing the link between parental wiccaphobia and delinquent behaviour among street children in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It offers insights into how societal misconceptions about witchcraft, particularly within family and religious contexts, drive vulnerable children to the streets, exposing them to severe physical abuse, neglect, and social exclusion. The study emphasizes that these cultural beliefs not only lead to direct harm but also set in motion a cycle of delinquency, as the children, deprived of care and protection, resort to survival mechanisms like theft,

begging, and substance abuse. It underscores the critical role of cultural, religious, and community structures in either reinforcing or challenging such harmful practices.

Further research could explore interventions aimed at mitigating the effects of wiccaphobia and providing support for street children. Research focusing on the role of education, community engagement, and legal frameworks in reshaping public understanding of witchcraft accusations and their implications for children's welfare would offer valuable perspectives on addressing the root causes of abuse. Additionally, more studies could investigate the long-term psychological impacts of these traumatic experiences, providing a deeper understanding of how these children can navigate and reintegrate into the society or be healed from such profound trauma.

Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations;

- i. *There should be community awareness campaigns aimed at dispelling myths about witchcraft and addressing the stigma associated with wiccaphobia. These campaigns can foster understanding and promote acceptance of street children.*
- ii. *There should be a support network for families affected by wiccaphobia, helping them to understand the psychological impact on their children and offering strategies to combat stigma and foster support.*
- iii. *The government should develop mobile outreach programmes that can reach street children in various*

locations, offering psychological support, health services, and educational resources, while also addressing issues related to wiccaphobia.

- iv. The study advocates for the immediate implementation of policies and laws that protect children from discrimination based on familial beliefs or societal misconceptions regarding witchcraft, ensuring that all children, regardless of their background, receive equal treatment.
- v. There is need for community engagement activities to promote cultural understanding and acceptance, this will allow street children to participate in activities that build confidence and foster community bonds.

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